

Evaluating carbon taxation policy to incentivize low carbon energy resources

Abstract:

Man-made green house gases are the main cause of global warming. Changes in temperature and hence environment are a danger to the survival of the whole planet. Climate change is unprecedented not just for its impact, but also in response to this challenge. Effective climate policies are a great solution to encourage low-carbon resources. This paper evaluates how policymakers can employ carbon taxes to promote a future with more sustainable energy sources. The paper provides an overview of this research background, underlining both urgency for climate action and the need for policy interventions that promote clean and inexpensive alternatives to fossil fuels. It looks into the scientific basis of climate change –how greenhouse gasses become warmer and its anticipated effect on natural and human systems. The core of this paper lies in anthropogenic carbon dioxide taxes, analyzing its main principles, strategies for implementation and the economic logic behind using market forces to check carbon-intense activities. The analysis evaluates various carbon pricing systems, such as cap-and-trade and direct tax structures, and explores their respective advantages, challenges and practical applications in the real world. The impact of carbon taxes is studied comprehensively from economic, environmental and social standpoints. The paper examines potential effects on patterns of energy consumption, investments in low-carbon technologies, job creation, and the overall competitiveness of industries. It also considers the profitability consequences of carbon pricing policies and potentially of measures to lighten regressive effects on vulnerable populations. It sums up main harvests and policy pointer for creation of carbon tax systems that own advantages, covering for their disadvantages, international cooperation. The research paper emphasizes the position of carbon pricing in achieving global climate goals and to a fair low-carbon energy future.

Chapter I: Introduction

Due to the increase in both the intensity and frequency of storms, heat waves, extreme dry spells, and even the occurrence of viral diseases in varying parts of the world, climate change is an impending disaster that requires urgent solutions and interventions. Bangladesh is grappling with a myriad of environmental issues, including air, water, and soil pollution, encroachment of public properties, ecosystem degradation, resource depletion, improper waste management, and biodiversity loss¹. The carbon taxation has been adopted as an effective policy instrument which may indicate to the low carbon resources. Carbon pricing, particularly through carbon taxes, is a crucial tool for reducing greenhouse gas emissions². Climate change, which is occasioned mostly by green house gases in the atmosphere due to man's activities, poses a real threat to all living things on planet earth. Basically the use of fossil energy sources in electricity generation as well as in industries has also played a role in the rise in the emission of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere through direct emissions. Therefore, the use of renewable resources of energy has been deemed very important to all due to the many vices of non-renewable resources of energy.

Carbon pricing is expected to attain the climate goals through several functions³. Carbon taxation in this sense as a market instrument aims to encourage ecological direction as it seeks to put a cost on activities that discharge carbon into the environment. Carbon taxation involves placing a financial cost on the use of fossil energy utilities in a bid to influence the consumers to look for optimization on the usage of renewable energy resources as well as increase their acquisition of energy efficient equipment. As for the policy of implementing carbon taxation, people may accept and reject based on multidimensional views. This can be achieved through regular impact reporting, stakeholder engagement and by directing revenue generated from the carbon tax towards supporting clean energy initiatives for low-income households⁴. The impact of the carbon taxation policy on the options available in energy sector, basic economic indicators and reduction of emission rates should be evaluated for decision making of the policy.

¹ Bahreen Khan, 'Efficacy and implementation gap in the core environmental laws of Bangladesh: an overview, Dhaka University Law Journal, vol 33, issue 1, 2022, page 33

² Luminita Ionescu, 'Climate Policies, Carbon Pricing, and Pollution Tax: Do Carbon Taxes Really Lead to a Reduction in Emissions?' (2019) 11(1) Geopolitics, History, and International Relations 92

³ Satoshi Kojima and Kenji Asakawa, 'Carbon pricing: a key instrument to facilitate low carbon transition' (2016) Institute for Global Environmental Strategies

⁴ Commonwealth Carbon Tax Model Law Launched to Help Countries Reduce Greenhouse Gas Emissions' (Commonwealth,2023)

Chapter II: Climate Change Science

Global warming can be described as the study of all angle of climate change together with their implications for the world, as well as the conventions, treaties, and rules that were established to address the impacts of global warming; this is a very extensive area of study. From the present climate change scholarly articles, it is clear that climate change exists and is a result of man made actions. Climate change has been noted, proved and confirmed by Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) and other scientific firms all over the world which provides enough evidence that climate of the earth is deteriorating due to some activities carried out by man⁵. The driver to climate change is the higher concentrations of the heat trapping compounds for instance CO₂, CH₄ and NO₂.

These greenhouse gases aid in holding heat from the sun hence contributing to a relatively rise in global average temperature. This is so because the phenomenon of the greenhouse effect is a normal occurrence which is essential in regulating climate on the planet Earth. With respect to the climatic change, the modulation of the climate has been interfered with by some anthropogenic factors such as the use of fossil energy and tree cutting. These have been experienced around several aspects which include; higher temperatures, the rising of the sea levels, prevalence of severe weathers, loss of habitats, and questionable sources of foods and water⁶. These impacts brought cataclysm on people's societies as well as the natural world; as a consequence, makes this global phenomenon deserve more focus.

Climate change has been a calamity that the entire world has come to measure and has sought to have frameworks and conventions on. Notable among these are:

United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC): The UNFCCC was signed in 1992 and is an international document whose long term goal is to prevent the enhancing of atmospheric concentrations of the specified GHG gases⁷.

Kyoto Protocol: Kyoto Protocol that was signed in 1997 and provides legally binding emission cutting targets for industrialised countries⁸.

⁵ Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, *Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* (2021)

⁶ C M Godde, D Mason-D'Croz, D E Mayberry, P K Thornton and M Herrero, 'Impacts of Climate Change on the Livestock Food Supply Chain: A Review of the Evidence' (2021) 28 *Global Food Security* 100488

⁷ United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change 1992

⁸ Kyoto Protocol 1997

Paris Agreement: Signed in Paris in 2015, this agreement entered into force in November 2016 and is legally binding with the objective of limiting the emission of greenhouse gases in order to ensure that the average global temperature remains under the threshold of 2 degrees above that of pre-industrial levels, or preferably 1.5°C⁹. It also gives direction in areas of adaptation, financing and assistance to the developing countries which as postulated was most affected by the effects of climate change.

Bangladesh Environment Conservation Act, 1995: This act outlines legal procedures of conservation and protection of Bangladesh environment and climate change¹⁰.

Article 18A of the Bangladesh Constitution: The provision contains that the state to exercise reasonable and sensible use of the environment and natural resources with an aim of benefiting generations to come¹¹.

Bangladesh Climate Change Strategy and Action Plan (BCCSAP): The BCCSAP adopted in 2009 offers a frameworks as a country develops policies and measures to fight climate change through adaptation and reduction¹².

The largest part of the GHG emissions can be attributed to the use of fossil fuels in the production of electricity, transport, and industries. They are the major causes of enhanced levels of carbon dioxide, methane, and other green house gases in the atmosphere. During the process of fossil fuel combustion the carbon contained in these micro biomolecules is emitted as CO₂ in the atmosphere. This has been continuing for well over two centuries since the Industrial revolution; and thus green house gases have accumulated in the atmosphere to interfere with the natural carbon cycle.

Currently the world economy depends a lot in fossil and other carbonaceous products and this is the big challenge of moving to the green economy¹³. The developed countries over the years have heavily depended on fossil fuels as the main source of power. Still, this dependence is detrimental to the environment because it leads to the aggravation of the climate crisis¹⁴. However, there is a growing trend in the exploration and utilization of non-renewable sources of energy, the world energy mix is still largely controlled by fossil energies. The IEA has

⁹ Paris Agreement 2015

¹⁰ Bangladesh Environment Conservation Act, 1995

¹¹ Constitution of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, article 18A

¹² Bangladesh Climate Change Strategy and Action Plan 2009

¹³ Suaad Hadi Hassan Al-Taai, Green economy and sustainable development'(2021) *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* 779 012007

¹⁴ *ibid*

pointed out that anywhere in the globe, the likelihood of exploiting fossil fuel for primary energy in 2021 is around 81%; the likelihoods of consuming coal, oil and natural gas are 27%, 31% and 23% respectively¹⁵.

The transportation sector ranks high when it comes to emission of greenhouse gases, this is because most of the transport systems utilize petroleum products. Electricity generation, industries, and residential and commercial buildings are also major contributors to burning of fossil fuels. Switching from products that have their origin in oil and switching to renewable energy sources is not a small task and has to be done by the society. There are three key processes in such a transformation: disposal of technical constraints, handling of economic context, and encouragement of behavioral modification.

Chapter III: Carbon Taxation Mechanisms

Climate change issue in the world has been associated with the use of fossil fuels and carbons resources in the world¹⁶. Rather implementing the technological revolution and policy on its own, the shift to a low carbon economy is a daunting task that has to be implemented through incentives as well¹⁷. Carbon taxation measures like carbon taxes, and the cap and trade system have been promoted on this account because these tools raise the cost of emitting the greenhouse gases as well as encouraging the use of cleaner technologies and efficient technologies¹⁸. The world economy for many decades has been completely dependent on fossil fuels – coal, oil, and natural gas. They have been tapped to foster industrialization, mobility, generation of power and in numerous manufacturing activities as non-renewable sources of energy. But fossil fuel combustion emits CO₂ and a host of other green house gases to the atmosphere thus compounding the climate change dilemma. This is especially true despite the world moving towards the use of renewable energy sources like solar, wind and hydro power, however most of the energy is still obtained from fossil energy sources. As of 2021, worldwide, 81% of the world's primary energy was met from fossil fuels of which 27% was met by coal oil and the remaining 31% by oil and 23% by natural gas according to International Energy Agency¹⁹. In addition, it is essential to work on reducing emissions related to the energy sector.

¹⁵ International Energy Agency, *World Energy Outlook 2021* (2021)

¹⁶ Gouzée, N and Willems, S, 'A Carbon/Energy Tax for Sustainable Development' in Requier-Desjardins, D, Spash, C and van der Straaten, J (eds), *Environmental Policy and Societal Aims*

¹⁷ *ibid*

¹⁸ Edward B. Barbier, 'Reducing carbon dependency' in *A Global Green New Deal: Rethinking the Economic Recovery* (Cambridge University Press 2010) 35-96

¹⁹ International Energy Agency, *World Energy Outlook 2021* (2021)

All of this can be achieved by technological breakthroughs and policy measures that lead to more renewables in the power sector and increased energy efficiency everywhere else²⁰.

Renewable Energy Sources:

- a) Solar – Using the energy of the Sun by either capturing sun rays in PV systems and CSP technologies²¹.
- b) Wind – Energy derived from the kinetic energy of wind using wind turbines (onshore and offshore)²²
- c) Hydropower: the use of falling or flowing water's potential energy to generate electricity²³.
- d) Using Geothermal: This mechanism makes use of the heat energy from deep inside the earth to form steam and this will further rotate turbines that create electricity²⁴.
- e) Bioenergy: Use of biomass, in the form of agricultural residues, forestry waste and energy crops for production of biofuels or electricity generation²⁵

Energy efficiency

- a) Building efficiency: Improved insulation, energy-efficient appliances, environment friendly technology²⁶
- b) Smart building management solutions; Industrial efficiency: upgrade of industrial processes, implementation of energy management systems and combined heat and power (cogeneration) applications²⁷.
- c) Improve transportation efficiency: It includes fuel efficient cars electric vehicles and public mass transits too. Implementing advanced metering infrastructure and demand-side management for optimal energy use²⁸.

²⁰ Roberta Mann, 'To Tax or Not to Tax Carbon—Is That the Question?' (2009) 24(1) *Natural Resources & Environment* 44

²¹ Vikas V Pawar and Safia Farooqui, 'The Effectiveness of Renewable Energy Technologies in Reducing Greenhouse Gas Emissions' (International Conference on Industry 5.0: Sustainability & Innovations in Business, Coimbatore, August 2023)

²² *ibid*

²³ *ibid*

²⁴ *ibid*

²⁵ *ibid*

²⁶ Celina Filippín, 'Energy Efficiency in Buildings' in Konrad A Hofman (ed), *Energy Efficiency, Recovery and Storage* (Nova Science Publishers 2007) 223

²⁷ *ibid*

²⁸ *ibid*

To achieve the low-carbon energy sector, policies and incentives to facilitate research, development, deployment of such technologies and measures for energy efficiency are essential.

The basis of carbon taxation mechanisms is to internalize the external costs from the emission of greenhouse gases into the prices by putting a price on emitted CO₂²⁹. The mechanisms aim to make the use of fossil fuels more expensive, in the hope that businesses and individuals will switch from dirtier forms of energy and spend on innovations that increase energy efficiency. The two principal mechanisms of carbon taxation are carbon taxes and cap-and-trade/feed-in tariffs.

A carbon tax is a fee that would be imposed on the burning of carbon-based fuels, such as coal, oil and gasoline in proportion to their carbon content. This tax could be implemented on the producers, importers or consumers of these fuels, and there is also plenty room for the revenue to be used in several ways- from funding clean energy projects or supporting low-income families to reducing other taxes, among others. A carbon tax is designed to raise the cost of using fossil fuels in order to make them less attractive, and at the same time encourage a transition to clean energy sources as well as practices that use energy more efficiently³⁰. A carbon tax ensures that the market fully accounts for the implicit environmental costs of carbon emissions, addressing a pervasive market failure in which fossil fuels have historically been underpriced.

Cap-and-Trade System—A market-based approach for reducing greenhouse gas emissions where a cap is set on the total allowable emission of a particular pollutant³¹. This sets a cap or limit on the total quantity of emissions that can come from the sectors/industries covered by the cap. and/or auction emission allowances or permits to these entities, allowing them to emit a defined amount of greenhouse gases³². Any company that produces emissions below its allocated allowance can sell the permits on to companies whose allowances are breached³³. This establishes a market for emission permit trading, which would encourage companies to develop and implement clean technologies and initiatives to become more energy efficient in

²⁹ Lee Godden, Jacqueline Peel, Alexander Zahar, 'Putting a price on carbon: Regulatory models and emissions trading schemes' in *Australian Climate Law in Global Context* (Cambridge University Press 2012) 164-198

³⁰ *ibid*

³¹ Chen Y and Hafstead M, 'Using a Carbon Tax to Meet US International Climate Pledges' (Resources for the Future, 2016)

³² *ibid*

³³ *ibid*

order to decrease their emissions while also being able to sell unused permits³⁴. The advantage of a cap-and-trade system is that it allows companies flexibility, so they can use the most cost-effective methods to cut emissions³⁵. That could mean taking steps within their own operations or buying permits from other firms in more cost-effective location³⁶.

Carbon pricing policy may be used as there was a failure in the market to account for the environment deteriorating. By setting a price for carbon, these policies are designed to correct that historical mistake that has undervalued true costs of fossil fuels and their negative environmental impacts.

Economic Waiver: Carbon pricing mechanisms provide businesses and people with an economic incentive to lower their carbon footprint³⁷. By raising the cost of carbon intensive activities, these policies encourage clean energy sources to be adopted, energy-efficient technologies developed, and unflagging environmentally friendly practices expanded³⁸.

Market Mechanism: Carbon pricing policies leverage market forces to drive down emissions. When businesses and consumers weigh their choices in terms of the cost of emissions, innovative and investment decisions made into low-carbon solutions get a boost³⁹.

Revenue Generator: With carbon taxes and emission permits auctioned in cap-and-trade systems, governments can earn substantial revenue from the pollution they produce. This income can be used in the fight against climate change for helping people adapt to it, conducting research and development related technology or methods for cleaner processing⁴⁰.

Flexibility and affordability: Cap-and-trade systems, in particular, offer flexibility by allowing companies to choose how best to reduce their emissions in ways that are cost-effective for them, either through their own actions or by buying permits from other entities who have achieved greater reductions⁴¹.

³⁴ UNEP, *Emissions Gap Report 2022* (27 October 2022)

³⁵ *ibid*

³⁶ *ibid*

³⁷ Andrea Baranzini, Jeroen van den Bergh, Stefano Carattini, Richard Howarth, Emilio Padilla and Jordi Roca, 'Seven Reasons to Use Carbon Pricing in Climate Policy' (Centre for Climate Change Economics and Policy Working Paper No 253, Grantham Research Institute on Climate Change and the Environment Working Paper No 224, February 2016)

³⁸ *ibid*

³⁹ *ibid*

⁴⁰ *ibid*

⁴¹ *ibid*

Global Cooperation: Carbon pricing policies can help bring about international cooperation and co-ordination to tackle climate change. By aligning the price of carbon across different jurisdictions, these policies establish a fair playing field and encourage broader participation in efforts to reduce emissions⁴².

While carbon-tax practices have sprung up as a potential tool for dealing with climate change, it is a relatively new and rough tool. The successful application and design of such practices must be based on the careful consideration economic, social, political factors which are needed for them to take root. Effective carbon pricing policies must be supplemented by other measures including regulations, incentives and public investment: to ensure a comprehensive and fair transition of society into a low-carbon economy⁴³

Chapter IV: Impacts of Carbon Taxation

Till now, carbon taxation has emerged as a popular policy choice by itself for mitigating climate change. As such, it also offers an incentive for moving towards a low carbon economy⁴⁴. The introduction of a carbon tax can have significant economic impacts, positive and negative. Economic models and empirical studies suggest that carbon taxation leads to economic impacts.

A carbon tax directly boosts the price of fossil fuels, which means that people who are consuming energy at home and in their cars will pay more for it⁴⁵. This may eventually affect budgets, industrial competitiveness worldwide, and the overall cost of living. Higher energy prices may cause consumers to seek energy-efficient products and services⁴⁶. This in turn provides an impetus for investment and innovation into low-carbon technology. It suggest that carbon taxes might lower GNP to a small extent, on the other hand, the revenue raised can be used to reduce other distortional taxes and thus mitigate any net negative impact. In addition, the transition towards a low-carbon economy could bring about new job opportunities in clean energy or other fields related to clean production⁴⁷.

⁴² *ibid*

⁴³ Ngwome, Gideon Fosoh, *The Legal Framework for Carbon Tax: A Case of Cameroon*, *Environmental Policy and Law*, vol. 53, no. 1, pp. 77-92, 2023

⁴⁴ Myanna Dellinger, *Carbon Taxation for Climate Change Mitigation*, 11 *LSU J. of Energy L. & Resources* (2023)

⁴⁵ Matlub Ul Alam, 'Carbon tax on vehicles and the possible aftermath' *The Daily Star* (25 June, 2023)

⁴⁶ *ibid*

⁴⁷ *ibid*

Carbon taxation may impose uneven burdens on third world country like Bangladesh and low-income households which spend a larger proportion of their income on goods and services that are energy-intensive in nature⁴⁸. Measure such as revenue recycling or targeted assistance are needed to address these distribution concerns. By increasing the cost of fossil fuels, carbon taxation provides a financial incentive for people not to produce or use them. As a result, reversion low carbon power sources and energy saving measures reduces greenhouse gas emissions⁴⁹. Higher fossil fuel prices can also make renewable sources like solar, wind and hydropower more attractive economically. For example, Bangladesh has a hydro powerplant in Kaptai. In this way new forms of energy are installed sooner rather than later. Besides, carbon taxation technology companies will no doubt develop technologies that improve energy use in various sectors (including buildings, transportation and industry), and consumers will reduce unnecessary energy consumption.

In the case of *Dr Mohiuddin Farooque, et al. v. Bangladesh (Ministry of Communication)* The Court ruled that the respondents had not exercised adequate measures of regulation to curb pollution levels hence ordered measures that would reduce the impacts.⁵⁰

Rabia Bhuiyan MP vs. Ministry of LGRD; it was the case where the petitioner had filed a writ petition against the government for its failure to abide by the Environment Conservation Act 1995 and the Environmental Conservation Rules 1997.⁵¹

Urgenda Foundation v. The Netherlands, in 2015, the Hague District Court decided that the Dutch government has to decrease greenhouse gas emissions by at least 25% compared to 1990 levels by the year 2020 to bear the due diligence burden of protection of Dutch citizens against the climate change imminent danger.⁵²

Although carbon taxation has emerged as an emission reduction policy tool, it is necessary to study its costs and benefits in comparison with other methods.

Command-and-control regulations, such as emission standards or technological requirements can be very effective in achieving targeted goals for reducing emissions⁵³. But they do not always allow the same leeway from market-based instruments like carbon taxes in terms of

⁴⁸ Dr Sadiq Ahmed and Dr Bazlul H. Khonker, 'Towards a carbon tax for Bangladesh' The Financial Express (24 April 2019)

⁴⁹ *ibid*

⁵⁰ *Dr Mohiuddin Farooque, et al. v. Bangladesh* 22 BLD (HCD) 2002 345

⁵¹ *Rabia Bhuiyan, MP v Secretary, Ministry of LGRD and Others* 59 DLR (AD) (2007)

⁵² *Urgenda Foundation v. The Netherlands* [2015] HAZA C/09/00456689

⁵³ Mohammad Abu Yusuf, 'On carbon pricing and taxation' The Financial Express (20 May, 2023)

cost efficiency. In terms of cars, older vehicles emit much more CO₂ than the newer vehicles. Many automobile companies are now shifting to manufacturing electric cars such as Tesla which is more environment friendly than diesel cars. Bangladesh has levied taxes on buying 2nd car⁵⁴. For clean technologies energy efficiency initiatives or research and development, the adoption of low-carbon options can be stimulated through subsidies⁵⁵. However, these may prove expensive for government and distort signals in markets. Cap-and-trade or "emissions trading" systems put an overall limit on emissions and allow companies to buy/ sell pollution credits⁵⁶. These allow flexibility and cost efficiency, whereas carbon taxes might be more difficult to implement or monitor. Combining carbon taxes with other policy tools such as regulations, subsidies or cap-and-trade systems can create an integrated and mutually supportive mix of policies for the transition to low-carbon future⁵⁷.

Chapter V: Conclusion and Recommendation

Transition to sustainable society is perhaps one of the world's most required sociopolitical transformations that are derived from the scientifically established fact of environmental degradation, climate change and resource scarcity due to dependence on fossil fuels. One of the common market tools for managing this kind of change is carbon taxation as it puts a face to society cost of more concentration of greenhouse gasses into the price of carbon link activities. It is hoped that such solutions that include carbon taxes and cap and trade systems will correct for the market failures that result from assigning a price to carbon emissions that will prompt businesses as well as people to decrease their levels of emissions and embrace more effective options. While carbon taxation might seem to impose negative impacts on energy costs and GDP in the short run its positive outcomes include technological innovation and restructuring consumer behavior, revenue generation for distribution issues and promotion of the low-carbon economy. Carbon taxing can in a great way achieve the reduction of greenhouse gases emissions, promotion of energy efficiency, and development of cleaner systems and low carbon technologies in the economy. Adopted by legal and judicial works pointing out the importance of climate change, carbon pricing such as taxation and cap-and-trade is considered as among the most efficient policy instruments because they help to achieve

⁵⁴ Jasim Uddin, 'Carbon tax coming for 2nd car' The Business Standard (11 May, 2023)

⁵⁵ *ibid*

⁵⁶ Ngwome, Gideon Fosoh, The Legal Framework for Carbon Tax: A Case of Cameroon, Environmental Policy and Law, vol. 53, no. 1, pp. 77-92, 2023

⁵⁷ *ibid*

the utmost value of the emission reductions that would be feasible in every country at the least possible costs.

There are important suggestions which have great significance in the case of implementing carbon taxation policies, namely creating an effective legal and institutional environment, gradual implementing of carbon tax rates and the use of carbon tax revenues. There should be a well-articulated policy for carbon taxation which is supported by laws and policies of the country, so that the coverage, monitoring, and enforcement of carbon taxation is well defined providing credibility to the entire system. This framework should also involve provisions of the processes that will enable stakeholders and the general public to be involved in the process as well as have access to sufficient information and the role that has to be played: on the premise of acceptance. In order to minimize the economic shocks and give stakeholders time to adapt, recommendations come with an initial small carbon tax rate that is gradually raised at specific intervals. This can be supported by phase in schedules, with high emission levels, and such measures as promotion of investment in clean technologies, and other measures of assistance to the worst affected regions and communities. Thus, it remains necessary to use revenue recycling measures to mitigate the possible regressive consequences and ensure people's support⁵⁸. These mechanisms include; Using the revenues accrued from the carbon tax to offer special tax exemptions or rebates to the vulnerable groups, reducing other inefficient taxes, formulating and implementing research and development projects in clean sources of energy. Thus, through the proper implementation of the revenue recycling framework, the policymakers balance the social acceptance, and facilitate a sustainable transition to the low carbon economy. Altogether, these recommendation: the comprehensive legal and regulatory requirements, gradual carbon taxation with step-by-step increases and the revenue recirculation policies will assist in achieving the successful implementation, long term sustenance and public acceptance of the carbon taxation policies for a transition towards low carbon economy.

⁵⁸ Macaluso N and others, 'The Impact of Carbon Taxation and Revenue Recycling on U.S. Industries' (2018) 9 Climate Change Economics

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